

PROBLEMS IN IMPROVING THE STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF THE ENTERPRISE

ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЕМ

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Abstract. This thesis discusses the problem of improving the strategic management of sustainable development in industrial enterprises. Disadvantages of strategic management of industrial enterprises are related to the decrease in the growth rates of the global and local economy, the specific features of the development of socio-economic relations under international sanctions. The main problem of the research is related to the imperfect strategic management of the enterprise's investment policy, which leads to the slowing down of the company's development and decrease in competitiveness.

Key word: strategic management, development, strategy, negatively affect.

Аннотация: В данной диссертации рассматривается проблема совершенствования стратегического управления устойчивым развитием промышленных предприятий. Недостатки стратегического управления промышленными предприятиями связаны со снижением темпов роста мировой и локальной экономики, особенностями развития социально-экономических отношений в условиях международных санкций. Основная проблема исследования связана с несовершенством стратегического управления инвестиционной политикой предприятия, что приводит к замедлению развития компании и снижению конкурентоспособности.

Ключевые слова: стратегическое управление, развитие, стратегия, негативно влиять.

Strategic management is one of the main elements of successful development of enterprises. A well-designed strategy allows you to define development goals and priorities, optimize resources, make informed decisions, and effectively manage changes in the external and internal environment.

Of course, the long-term success of any enterprise depends on the developed strategy. If the development strategy of the enterprise is not developed with one or another error, this situation does not allow the enterprise to take a stable and strong position in the market. Modern science and practice have extensive experience in strategic planning and management, but many strategies still cannot adapt to the changing conditions of the external and internal environment. This shows that not all problems of strategic management have yet been solved, and this situation is primarily related to the development of mechanisms of strategic stability of enterprise development.

However, modern enterprises face a number of problems and difficulties related to the improvement of strategic management. And below we will mention some of them

1. Lack of understanding of strategy. One of the main problems is the lack of understanding of the strategy by employees at all levels of the organization. It often happens that the strategy is formulated at the top level, but does not reach the lower level implementers. This leads to the loss of the integrity of the actions and compliance with the set goals.
2. Inadequate adaptation to changes. The rapidly changing external environment requires enterprises to be flexible and respond quickly to changes. However, many organizations are not prepared for such challenges and do not know how to adapt their strategy to new conditions.
3. Inadequate use of information technology. Modern information technologies offer great opportunities for improving strategic management, but many companies do not fully use them. This leads to loss of competitive advantage and management efficiency.¹

Thus, improving the strategic management of enterprises requires a comprehensive approach and consideration of various aspects such as strategy development, resource allocation, employee motivation, and control of achievement of set goals. The correct application of these methods and approaches allows enterprises to effectively develop and achieve success in the modern conditions of the market economy, and it allows you to simulate schemes of business processes.²

Also, the objective reasons caused by the need to transition to the innovative type of development of economic systems require a comprehensive solution to the problems of effective cooperation of scientific, technical and economic factors in the entire innovation-investment process. In our opinion, the rational combination of technological and economic potentials is the central issue of managing the innovation-investment process. Table 1 below provides an assessment of the factors affecting the stability of the enterprise. It analyzes the main innovative trends in enterprises and the factors that negatively affect the introduction of innovations, as well as the factors that ensure the development and support of innovations.

Table 1

Analysis of factors affecting the stability of enterprises³

№	Factors	The results of the influence of factors
1	Knowledge and skills	Direct management in production enterprises (laws of market economy) lack of knowledge and skills in the introduction of innovative management prevents to do.
2	Level of concentration	A high degree of centralization makes lower level managers more creative limits the possibility of a creative approach in thinking and management
3	Communication system	Poor organization of the communication system or the manager. In some cases, they cannot effectively use information and news causing on-time delivery problems
4	Agreement relations	The manager and the employee do not know clearly

¹ Shevchenko, G.; Ustinovichius, L.; Walasek, D. The evaluation of the contractor's risk in implementing the investment projects in construction by using the verbal analysis methods. *Sustainability* 2019, 11, 2660. [CrossRef]

² Ansoff I. Strategies for Diversification. *Harvard Business Review*, 1957, pp. 113-124

³ Prepared by the authors as a result of research

		the assigned tasks and follow them failure to do so hinders the development of the management process
5	To innovations interest	Low interest in innovation by managers i.e. lack of flexibility in management
6	Encouragement	Inadequate development of incentive system in management reduces interest in introducing innovative management

The large number of factors makes it possible to classify them according to certain characteristics. The external factors of the enterprise include: anti-crisis policy of the state in the economic sphere; demographic situation in the country; political stability; progress of science and technology; development of transport infrastructure. Internal factors are formed in the internal environment of the enterprise, in its subsystems (employees, production, marketing, sales, finance, organizational structure). Management of internal factors allows the enterprise to determine reserves of stability strengthening and to quickly manage production in case of changes in external factors. The systematic development of the enterprise is carried out by successively passing the stages from centralization to decentralization. This means that every element of the enterprise becomes planned and organized. In essence, the transition to a decentralized scheme of management by the enterprise also changes the management system as a goal-directed external influence on the object, to change it to another state. Development of the elements of the enterprise to the level of independent decision-making in the conditions of an unknown external environment is the necessity of ensuring the competitiveness of the enterprise. On the other hand, the enterprise must have certain characteristics as a whole in the external environment, as a goal-oriented development. The main of them is controllability. Management of the investment policy of enterprises, which leads to incorrect determination of investment policy. The size and direction of investment capital formation hinders sustainable development.

Thus, studying the problems of improving the strategic management of enterprises made it possible to identify the main problems and obstacles facing modern organizations. The results of the study showed that for effective management, it is necessary to take into account internal and external factors, as well as constantly analyze and correct the company's strategies.

To solve these problems, enterprises are recommended to introduce modern management methods, such as the system of balancing indicators, management by objectives, strategic planning, etc. In addition, it is important to ensure transparency and openness in the management process, to ensure the motivation of employees, and to create conditions for continuous training and professional development of employees.

Thus, the further development of strategic management of enterprises requires continuous improvement and adaptation to changing market conditions and the internal environment of the company. Scientific research on these issues plays an important role in increasing the competitiveness and successful development of organizations.

References:

1. Ansoff I. Strategies for Diversification. Harvard Business Review, 1957, pp. 113-124

2. Shevchenko, G.; Ustinovichius, L.; Walasek, D. The evaluation of the contractor's risk in implementing the investment projects in construction by using the verbal analysis methods. Sustainability 2019, 11, 2660. [CrossRef]
3. Heo, B.Y.; Heo, W.H. Economic analysis of disaster management investment effectiveness in Korea. Sustainability 2019, 11, 3011. [CrossRef]
4. Gong, D.C.; Kao, C.W.; Peters, B.A. Sustainability investments and production planning decisions based on environmental management. J. Clean. Prod. 2019, 225, 196–208. [CrossRef]

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